

Vulvoperineal Angiomyofibroblastoma in A Postmenopausal Woman: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Angiomyofibroblastoma is a rare benign mesenchymal neoplasm of the lower genital tract, described mainly in women of reproductive age. Its nonspecific clinical presentation and its similarity to other benign or locally aggressive vulvar lesions, such as aggressive angiomyxoma, may complicate the initial diagnosis. Early recognition of this entity is essential to avoid unnecessarily aggressive surgical treatments and to ensure appropriate management.

Case Report: We present the case of a 51-year-old woman who attended a gynecological consultation due to a vulvar foreign-body sensation of approximately one year of evolution, characterized by slow growth and absence of pain. Physical examination revealed a well-circumscribed mass located in the right labium majus, near the urethral meatus, without signs of inflammation or inguinal lymphadenopathy. Soft-tissue ultrasound showed a well-defined hypoechoic mass without significant Doppler flow. Surgical management was performed through complete excision of the lesion with primary closure, without complications. Histopathological examination revealed a well-circumscribed tumor composed of alternating hypercellular and hypocellular areas, abundant capillary vascularity, and minimal mitotic activity. Immunohistochemical analysis showed positivity for vimentin and hormone receptors, confirming the diagnosis of angiomyofibroblastoma. Surgical margins were negative. The postoperative course was favorable, and no recurrence was documented during clinical and imaging follow-up.

Conclusion: Vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma is a rare entity that should be considered in the differential diagnosis of vulvar masses. Definitive diagnosis is established through histopathological evaluation, and complete surgical excision represents a curative treatment with an excellent prognosis.

KEYWORDS: Angiomyofibroblastoma; Vulva; Mesenchymal tumors; Vulvar mass; Benign tumors; Benign soft tissue neoplasm.

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INTRODUCTION

Angiomyofibroblastoma is a rare benign mesenchymal neoplasm of the soft tissues of the lower genital tract, described predominantly in women of reproductive age and exceptionally in men. Its most common location is the vulvoperineal region, although cases have also been reported in the vagina, urethra, paraurethral region, uterus, and adnexa.

In men, it has been described in the inguinoscrotal and perineal regions as well as in the spermatic cord. Since its initial description by Fletcher and colleagues in the early 1990s, only a limited number of cases have been reported, making it difficult to establish precise incidence and prevalence data.¹²

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Clinically, it usually presents as a well-circumscribed mass with slow growth, variable size, and generally painless characteristics, with an evolution ranging from weeks to several years. In some cases, accelerated growth during pregnancy has been reported, a phenomenon attributed to the expression of estrogen and progesterone receptors. Due to its nonspecific clinical presentation, angiomyofibroblastoma may mimic other benign vulvar lesions, such as vestibular gland cysts, lipomas, or fibromas, as well as tumors with locally aggressive behavior, particularly aggressive angiomyxoma, making accurate identification essential.¹³

Imaging studies, including ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging, can contribute to lesion characterization by assessing size, margins, and relationships with adjacent structures, as well as supporting surgical planning. However, definitive diagnosis is established through histopathological examination, which typically reveals a well-circumscribed tumor composed of spindle-shaped cells with minimal mitotic activity arranged within a characteristic vascular stroma.²³

The treatment of choice is complete surgical excision, which is associated with a favorable prognosis and a low recurrence rate, although intraoperative bleeding has been described as a possible complication due to the vascular component of the tumor. After complete excision, angiomyofibroblastoma shows a low tendency for local recurrence. In contrast, aggressive angiomyxoma has a high probability of local recurrence, estimated between 33% and 72% of cases, due to its infiltrative nature and the difficulty of achieving complete resection, with frequent extension into the pelvic cavity and involvement of adjacent structures such as nerves and mucous glands.¹²

The objective of this article is to present a clinical case of vulvoperineal angiomyofibroblastoma, a rare benign mesenchymal neoplasm of the lower genital tract, and to describe its clinical, diagnostic, and histopathological characteristics, highlighting the importance of its recognition and of establishing an adequate differential diagnosis with other vulvar lesions with different biological behavior.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 51-year-old female patient, originally from Timucuy and residing in the city of Mérida, Yucatán, who works as a merchant. She is single and of Catholic religion. She attended a gynecological consultation due to a sensation of a vulvar foreign body of approximately one year of evolution, characterized by slow and progressive growth, without pain, bleeding, discharge, or signs of local inflammation. The discomfort caused inconvenience during walking and personal hygiene, which prompted her to seek medical evaluation.

Her past medical history included systemic arterial hypertension of eleven years of evolution, treated with losartan 50 mg orally once daily, with adequate control. Her surgical history included a total abdominal hysterectomy for uterine fibromatosis without complications, as well as a

previous cholecystectomy due to gallstones, both with satisfactory outcomes. Regarding her gynecological and obstetric history, menarche occurred at 12 years of age, onset of sexual activity at 19 years, one sexual partner, gravida one, para one, and menopause at 45 years of age. A recent cervical cytology was negative for intraepithelial lesions or malignancy, and mammography showed no abnormalities. She denied relevant family history of gynecologic malignancies, breast cancer, or known genetic diseases.

From a psychosocial perspective, the patient was functional and independent, followed a traditional mixed diet, and denied tobacco, alcohol, or illicit drug use. No cultural or linguistic barriers limiting access to healthcare were identified; however, the painless nature of the lesion contributed to delayed consultation.

On general physical examination, the patient was in good overall condition, with vital signs within normal limits (blood pressure 120/80 mmHg, heart rate 88 beats per minute, respiratory rate 18 breaths per minute), weight 82 kg, and height 1.60 m, with a body mass index of 32 kg/m². Gynecological examination revealed a mass located in the upper third of the right labium majus, measuring approximately 5 × 5 cm, with regular borders, soft consistency, mobility, and no tenderness on palpation. There were no changes in skin coloration, signs of infection, ulceration, or discharge. The lesion was located near the urethral meatus (Figure 1). Examination of the urethra and paraurethral region showed no abnormalities, and there were no associated urinary symptoms. The vaginal introitus appeared normal, without evidence of prolapse or pelvic organ displacement. Bimanual palpation did not reveal adnexal masses, and no bilateral inguinal lymphadenopathy was detected.

As part of the diagnostic evaluation, a soft tissue ultrasound was performed, revealing a well-circumscribed hypoechoic vulvar mass measuring approximately 4.9 × 3.6 × 3.0 cm. Doppler evaluation showed no significant vascular flow. Additional imaging studies, such as magnetic resonance imaging, were not performed due to resource limitations; however, this did not modify the therapeutic approach, since diagnostic and therapeutic excision of the lesion had already been planned from the initial evaluation.

Based on the clinical and imaging findings, the differential diagnoses included Bartholin gland cyst, epidermoid cyst, vulvar lipoma, fibroma, and benign mesenchymal tumors of the vulva.

Given the clinical characteristics of the lesion, its progressive growth, and the functional impact reported by the patient, surgical management was decided through wide excision of the tumor with vulvar reconstruction, performed by the gynecology and urogynecology service (Figure 2). The procedure was carried out under subarachnoid regional block. Cefalotin 1 g intravenously was administered as antibiotic prophylaxis prior to entering the operating room. Complete tumor resection was achieved without injury to adjacent

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structures, including the urethra, with an approximate surgical time of one hour, minimal blood loss, and no intraoperative complications. Vulvar reconstruction was performed by primary closure. Postoperative management included oral analgesics consisting of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and paracetamol for five days.

Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen revealed a well-circumscribed tumor lesion with regular contours, composed of a stroma with alternating hypercellular and hypocellular areas, containing abundant capillary-sized blood vessels irregularly distributed within a hyalinized-edematous stroma. Tumor cells displayed spindle-shaped or ovoid nuclei with eosinophilic cytoplasm, arranged in small groups or nests, occasionally concentrated around blood vessels. Mitotic activity was very low, and no areas of tumor

necrosis, hemorrhage, or cystic changes were identified. Surgical margins were free of tumor (Figure 3). Immunohistochemical analysis showed positivity for vimentin, as well as diffuse expression of estrogen and progesterone receptors, findings consistent with angiomyofibroblastoma.

The postoperative course was satisfactory. During follow-up visits, adequate healing of the surgical wound was observed, without evidence of dehiscence, infection, or pain. The patient reported complete resolution of the foreign-body sensation and good tolerance of the procedure. During one-year clinical and imaging follow-up, she remained asymptomatic, with no clinical or radiological evidence of tumor recurrence. Periodic gynecological surveillance was established, and the prognosis was considered favorable.

Figure 1. Right vulvar mass located in the upper third of the labium majus, measuring approximately 5 × 5 cm, with regular borders, smooth surface, and no apparent inflammatory changes, corresponding to the clinical lesion prior to surgical excision.

Figure 2. Surgical specimen following excision of the vulvar tumor. Two well-defined fragments are observed, with a solid appearance and soft consistency, corresponding to a Skene's gland cyst and an angiomyofibroblastoma, prior to histopathological processing.

Figure 3. Histological section showing proliferation of spindle-shaped cells within a loose stroma with abundant vascularity, without atypia, consistent with angiomyofibroblastoma.

DISCUSSION

Vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma is a rare entity among mesenchymal tumors of the lower genital tract, and its diagnosis represents a clinical challenge due to its nonspecific presentation and its similarity to other benign and locally aggressive vulvar lesions. This clinical overlap may lead to misdiagnosis and inappropriate therapeutic decisions if this entity is not considered in the differential diagnosis.¹³⁸

In the literature, vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma has been described with variable clinical presentations. Espinal-Rodríguez et al. reported the case of a 49-year-old woman with a vulvar mass of three years of evolution, with progressive growth and intense pain, involving both the labia majora and minora.⁴ This contrasts with the present case, in which the patient presented with a painless vulvar tumor of one year of evolution located in the right labium majus. In both cases, the initial clinical suspicion included more common benign vulvar lesions, reflecting the diagnostic difficulty of this entity. However, as in the case reported by those authors, the definitive diagnosis was established through histopathological examination after surgical excision. The postoperative course was favorable in both cases, without significant complications or documented recurrence during follow-up, reinforcing that complete surgical excision constitutes a curative treatment with an excellent prognosis when vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma is correctly identified.⁴

Shilpa et al. described a case of vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma in a 42-year-old woman who presented with a pedunculated, asymptomatic, and progressively enlarging mass with clinical features resembling a Bartholin gland cyst. In agreement with this report, the present case also showed a slowly growing lesion with a favorable outcome after surgical excision; however, our patient did not present with a pedunculated lesion and was not completely asymptomatic. In both cases, the definitive diagnosis was established through histopathological examination, and the clinical course was favorable,

confirming that complete tumor resection is an effective curative treatment for this entity.⁵

Haroon et al. analyzed a large series of mesenchymal tumors of the female lower genital tract and demonstrated that angiomyofibroblastoma has a more favorable clinical behavior compared with aggressive angiomyxoma, with smaller tumor size and a significantly lower recurrence rate. These findings are consistent with the present case, in which a moderately sized, well-circumscribed vulvar lesion without evidence of local infiltration was documented, with a satisfactory clinical course following surgical excision. This study highlights the importance of accurate histopathological diagnosis to differentiate these entities, since aggressive angiomyxoma has a greater tendency for recurrence, particularly in large tumors. This underscores the relevance of an adequate differential diagnosis to guide treatment and follow-up.⁶

Similarly, Angelico et al. emphasize that stromal tumors of the female lower genital tract constitute a heterogeneous group of neoplasms with overlapping morphological and immunohistochemical features, which may generate diagnostic difficulties, particularly in the presence of unusual morphological variants. This observation is consistent with the present case, in which the definitive diagnosis of angiomyofibroblastoma was established through histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis, allowing differentiation from other entities such as aggressive angiomyxoma or cellular angiofibroma, which have different prognostic and therapeutic implications. Accurate identification of this entity, based on comprehensive evaluation of clinical and pathological findings, is essential to avoid misdiagnosis and unnecessarily aggressive treatments.⁷ Among the main strengths in the management of this case was the appropriate initial clinical evaluation, complemented by soft-tissue ultrasound, which helped guide timely surgical treatment. Although advanced imaging studies such as magnetic resonance imaging were not available, this limitation did not modify the therapeutic approach, since diagnostic-therapeutic excision of the lesion had already been

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planned from the initial evaluation. Complete excision of the tumor with negative surgical margins not only resolved the patient's symptoms but also provided sufficient tissue to establish a definitive histopathological and immunohistochemical diagnosis. Subsequent clinical and imaging follow-up demonstrated a favorable course, without complications or recurrence.

This case highlights the importance of considering angiomyofibroblastoma in the differential diagnosis of vulvar masses, even when they present asymptotically or with minimal symptoms. It also underscores that an accurate diagnosis helps prevent unnecessarily aggressive surgical treatments and allows appropriate management with an excellent prognosis. Clinicopathological correlation is essential to establish the definitive diagnosis and determine appropriate follow-up. From the patient's perspective, the treatment outcome was satisfactory, with complete resolution of symptoms and a clear understanding of the benign nature of the lesion and the importance of medical follow-up.

CONCLUSION

Vulvar angiomyofibroblastoma is a rare benign mesenchymal neoplasm whose recognition is essential due to its clinical similarity to other vulvar lesions with different biological behavior. Definitive diagnosis is established through histopathological examination, and simple surgical excision represents a curative treatment with an excellent prognosis. The presentation of this case reinforces the importance of considering this entity in the differential diagnosis of vulvar masses in order to avoid aggressive treatments and ensure appropriate management.

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Conflict of Interest: None.

Ethical Considerations: The patient was fully informed about the diagnosis, the interventions performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures and for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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